

**Synthesis and Antifungal Activity of some
1,4-Disubstituted-thiosemicarbazides,
2,5-Disubstituted-1,3,4-thiadiazoles and
3,4-Disubstituted-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles**

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THIOSEMICARBAZIDES possessing $-N-C=S$ group, is an essential structural feature responsible for various biocidal¹ properties. The acidic cyclisation of thiosemicarbazides leads to 1,3,4-thiadiazoles, which also display various biological activities^{2,3}. Various substituted-triazoles⁴ are also known to exhibit significant biological activities. Keeping these facts in view, the title compounds have been synthesised and some of them screened for their antifungal activity against two fungi, viz. *Aspergillus niger* and *Helminthosporium oryzae*.

1-Aryloxyacetyl/aroyle-4-aryl thiosemicarbazides (1-15) were prepared by refluxing a mixture of aryloxyacetyl/aroyle hydrazines and aryl isothiocyanates. Acidic cyclisation of the thiosemicarbazides (1-15) afforded 2-arylamino-5-aryloxymethyl/aryl-1,3,4-thiadiazoles (16-30). 3-Aryloxymethyl/aryl-4-aryl-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazoles (31-45) were synthesised by refluxing requisite hydrazines with aryl isothiocyanates in sodium hydroxide (Scheme 1). Structures of the compounds were established by elemental analysis and spectral data.

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Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 710 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (DMSO- d_6 + $CDCl_3$) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference at 90 MHz. The reactions were monitored by tlc. The required hydrazines were prepared by known method. Procedure for one compound of each step has been described in sequel. The physical and spectral data of compounds are given in Table 1.

1-(3', 4'-Dimethylphenoxy) acetyl-4-(4''-methoxyphenyl)thiosemicarbazide (4): A methanolic solution

of 3,4-dimethylphenoxyacetyl hydrazine (1.94 g, 0.01 mol) and 4-methoxyphenyl isothiocyanate (1.65 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed for 3 h and then cooled. The resulting solid was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (3.04 g, 85%), m.p. 124° (Found : N, 11.49 ; S, 8.81. $C_{18}H_{21}N_3O_3S$ requires : N, 11.70 ; S, 8.91%).

2-(4''-Methoxyanilino)-5-(3', 4'-dimethylphenoxy) methyl-1,3,4-thiadiazole (19): The thiosemicarbazide (4 ; 3.59 g, 0.01 mol) was just dissolved in cold and concentrated sulphuric acid. The mixture was kept at room temperature for 2 h, stirred occasionally and then poured over crushed ice. The resulting solid was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (2.21 g, 65%), m.p. 192° (Found N, 12.20 ; S, 9.26. $C_{18}H_{19}N_3O_2S$ requires N, 12.32 ; S, 9.38%).

3-(3', 4'-Dimethylphenoxy)methyl-4-(4''-methylphenyl)-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole (33): A mixture of 3,4-dimethylphenoxyacetyl hydrazine (1.94 g, 0.01 mol) and 4-methylphenyl isothiocyanate (1.49 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml ; 8%) for 5 h, then cooled, poured into excess of water, stirred and filtered. The filtrate on acidification with cold dilute hydrochloric acid yielded a solid which was washed and recrystallised from aqueous ethanol, (2.30 g, 71%), m.p. 153° (Found : N, 12.81 ; S, 9.74. $C_{18}H_{19}N_3OS$ requires : N, 12.92 ; S, 9.85%).

Antifungal screening: Twentynine compounds were screened for their antifungal activity by agar-growth technique³ against two fungi, viz. *A. niger* and *H. oryzae* at three different concentrations, i.e. 1000, 100 and 10 ppm. The activity of the com-

TABLE I—PHYSICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd no *	R ¹	Yield %	M p. °C	ν_{max} (cm ⁻¹) ; δ
1	H	85	138	ν_{max} 3 300 (NH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 360 (C-CH ₃), 1 040, 1 240 (=C-O-C), 1 100 (C=S); δ 2.0, 2.1 (6H, s, 2×Ar-CH ₃), 4.4 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 6.4-7.1 (8H m, ArH), 8 17 (2H br, 2×NH), 8.8 (1H, s, CONH)
2	Cl	80	171	ν_{max} 3 320 (NH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 100 (C=S), 710 (C-Cl)
3	CH ₃	82	162	ν_{max} 3 320 (NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 100 (C=S)
4	CH ₃ O	85	124	ν_{max} 3 300 (NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 360 (C-CH ₃), 1 020, 1 240 (=C-O-C), 1 120 (C=S), δ 2.0, 2.1 (6H s, 2×CH ₃), 3.7 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.5 (2H s, OCH ₃), 6.5-7.1 (7H, m, ArH), 8.2 (2H br, 2×NH), 8.85 (1H, s, CONH)
5	C ₂ H ₅ O	82	149	—
6	H	66	178	ν_{max} 3 300 (NH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 340 (NO ₂), 1 080 (C=S)
7	Cl	56	186	—
8	CH ₃	69	166	ν_{max} 3 320 (NH), 1 670 (C=O), 1 100 (C=S), δ 2.1 (3H s, CH ₃), 6.7-7.2 (7H, m, ArH), 8 15 (2H br, 2×NH), 9 1 (1H, s, CONH)
9	CH ₃ O	79	197	—
10	C ₂ H ₅ O	69	190	ν_{max} 3 280 (NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 340 (NO ₂), 1 080 (C=S)
11	H	75	190	—
12	Cl	63	189	—
13	CH ₃	72	191	ν_{max} 3 500 (OH), 3 300 (NH), 1 700 (C=O), 1 380 (C-CH ₃), 1 100 (C=S)
14	CH ₃ O	65	165	—
15	C ₂ H ₅ O	66	184	ν_{max} 3 480 (OH), 3 340 (NH), 1 680 (C=O), 1 110 (C=S)
16	H	60	181	ν_{max} 3 240 (NH), 1 590 (C=N), 1 020, 1 240 (=C-O-C), 700 (C-S-C)
17	Cl	70	215	—
18	CH ₃	60	192	ν_{max} 3 200 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 700 (C-S-C)

(Table 1 Contd.)

19	CH ₃ O	65	192	$\nu_{\max}$ 3 200 (NH), 1 580 (C=N), 1 360 (C-CH ₃), 1 080, 1 250 (=C-O-C), 700 (C-S-C); δ 2.1, 2.5 (6H, s, 2×CH ₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 5.3 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 6.7-7.9 (7H, m, ArH), 8.85 (1H, br, NH)
20	C ₂ H ₅ O	72	197	—
21	H	59	190	—
22	Cl	63	185	$\nu_{\max}$ 3 280 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 710 (C-S-C); δ 6.8-7.6 (7H, m, ArH), 8.85 (1H, br, NH)
23	CH ₃	52	208	—
24	CH ₃ O	61	227	—
25	C ₂ H ₅ O	61	122	$\nu_{\max}$ 3 200 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 700 (C-S-C)
26	H	60	167	$\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 3 220 (NH), 1 600 (C=N), 700 (C-S-C)
27	Cl	54	218	—
28	CH ₃	62	143	$\nu_{\max}$ 3 480 (OH), 3 220 (NH), 1 580 (C=N), 700 (C-S-C)
29	CH ₃ O	65	105	—
30	C ₂ H ₅ O	64	145	—
31	H	57	161	$\nu_{\max}$ 2 560 (SH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 380 (C-CH ₃), 1 160 (C=S)
32	Cl	63	150	—
33	CH ₃	71	153	$\nu_{\max}$ 2 550 (SH), 1 610 (C=N), 1 370 (C-CH ₃), 1 020, 1 240 (=C-O-C), 1 120 (C=S); δ 2.0, 2.1, 2.15 (9H, s, 3×CH ₃), 4.7 (2H, s, OCH ₃), 6.45-7.3 (7H, m, ArH); peak for SH not observed
34	CH ₃ O	60	109	—
35	C ₂ H ₅ O	70	119	$\nu_{\max}$ 2 560 (SH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 020, 1 250 (=C-O-C), 1 100 (C=S)
36	H	51	195	—
37	Cl	71	215	$\nu_{\max}$ 2 550 (SH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 130 (C=S)
38	CH ₃	53	245	$\nu_{\max}$ 2 580 (SH), 1 580 (C=N), 1 360 (C-CH ₃), 1 120 (C=S); δ 2.2 (3H, s, CH ₃), 6.6-7.4 (7H, m, ArH)
39	CH ₃ O	56	197	—
40	C ₂ H ₅ O	51	178	—
41	H	57	274	$\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 2 600 (SH), 1 600 (C=N), 1 080 (C=S)
42	Cl	60	290	—
43	CH ₃	61	255	—
44	CH ₃ O	65	238	$\nu_{\max}$ 3 500 (OH), 2 560 (SH), 1 580 (C=N), 1 020, 1 250 (=C-O-C), 1 100 (C=S)
45	C ₂ H ₅ O	70	214	—

*1-5, 16-20, 31-35 (R=3,4-(CH₃)₂C₆H₃OCH₂-), 6-10, 21-25, 36-40 (R=2-Cl, 5-NO₂-C₆H₃-); 11-15, 26-30, 41-45 (R=4-OH-C₆H₄-); All compounds gave satisfactory N and S analyses.

pounds was compared with commercial fungicide carbendazim.

On the basis of average percentage inhibitions observed after 96 h, all the compounds were found to display moderate to good level of toxicity against both the fungi at 1000 ppm, but their toxicity decreased markedly on dilution at 100 and 10 ppm. They were, however, more toxic against *H. oryzae* than against *A. niger*. Compounds 19, 32 and 35 were found to be more fungicidal than the others and inhibited >40% growth of both the fungi at 10 ppm level and their activity (>80%) were quite comparable with carbendazim. Compounds 39 and 45 also inhibited >80% growth of *H. oryzae*. In general, triazoles and thiadiazoles exhibited invariably good activity than the thiosemicarbazides. Further, the presence of chlorine, alkoxy and/or aryloxy group invariably enhanced the fungitoxicity of the compounds.

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